

Policies and Reforms of Educational Systems in Somalia
(A Review of the Current Situation)

Dr. Abdishakur Sh. Hassan Faqih,

An Associate Professor – Faculty of Education at Mogadishu Univeristy

Abstract

Since the collapse of the Somali government in 1991, the education system Policies have not been reformed. There are many controversy steps to reform the policies and the legal framework but hardly been the subject of any steps forward. This study presents the current situation and how to improve the quality and minimum standard in near future. Meanwhile some efforts organized to initiate discussing education policy and act framework, but informal decentralized system in the country sparked much delays. At the same time, there is a risk of fragmentation in school management between public and private schools limiting the quality impact of education and skill development on students.

The Significance of the study focuses on the strengths and challenges in the current education policy to assist accessing a good quality education and help educational policy-makers, planners, and other interested parties to make appropriate decisions concerning accessibility and quality of education system in Somalia. The study uses a documentary study review method to collect and analyze data of texts and documents available in the ministry of education databases (EMIS), International NGO's, and search function provided by Google and

Google scholar. It concludes that the absence of central accreditation and quality assure institutions created poor quality outcomes, which completely affected the education system totally. The demand for policy reform is absolutely necessary to address the education qualities and standards in the current school system.

Eventually, the study recommends that emphasis to be given the whole education system policy and quality control assuring strategy mechanism, designed around the students and learning, build teachers' capacity, and engage all public and private sectors.

Keywords: Policy, Reforms, Educational Systems, Current Situation, Quality, Accreditation

1.1 Introduction

Globalization has exerted much pressure on governments of today to redefine their roles in relation to education. In today's world, educational policies have increasingly been thought about and made within the context of the pressure and requirements of globalization (Segrera, 2010).

The two main bases of globalization have been identified as information and innovation, which are highly knowledge intensive (Carnoy, 2005). Education, in this case, has been applied to the process of globalization through a knowledge economy. In the knowledge economy, education is a crucial factor to ensure economic productivity and competitiveness in the international context (Nogueira & Jaana, 2013).

Somalia needs to consider as it endeavors to attain the ideals of education goals. The identification policy priorities have been set

A Review of the Current Situation

within the context of the identified educational challenges prevailing in the country learnt by the institutions collapse consequences and the new constitution of federal administration challenges about specific policies and practices could be on the march.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Education scope is to promote national development. Even with this consensus, many differed opinions have come out as to: How we want to be the Somali education system? Who will benefits from that education? And why should the education policies reformed? Such questions arise because it is not clear as to whether education is a private or public good. Such differences have existed in Somalia leading to policy reforms. However, these policy reforms had a different intension leading to different outcomes. Since the government of Somalia collapsed, there has been great desire to revitalization Somali education policies systems toshift in education cycle.

1.3 Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study are:

- 1- To trace the reforms of education policies and standards in Somalia education system.
- 2- To identify current situation reform policies by the federal government to expand access to education and assure quality.
- 3- To identify challenges facing education system in Somalia.

1.4 Research questions

- 1- How has been the reform of education policies and standers in Somalia education system?

2- Is there a policy reformed by Somalia currently to expand access to education and assure quality?

3- Is there a challenge facing the education system in Somalia?

This study responds to these questions by examining education system from Somali perspective, and then proceeding to draw recommendations.

1.5 Significance of the study

The study is focusing on the strengths and challenges in the current education policy to assist accessing a good quality education and also help educational policy-makers, planners, and other interested parties making appropriate decisions concerning accessibility and quality of education system in Somalia.

1.6 Methodology

This study will look at the education systems of Somalia, and then explore their strengths and critics from experts' opinions. It used documentary study review method to collect and analyze data. Documentary review method of research involves the analysis of texts and documents that contain data in line with the research problems (Gaborone, 2006).

Documentary research is concerned with analysis, synthesis and interpretation of data to find patterns and generalized results so as to address research questions. The study conducted a literature search for qualitative studies published within the Somali education from International NGO's, Ministry of education databases (EMIS) and computer search function provided by Google and Google scholar.

A Review of the Current Situation

The study employs critical case sampling that involves selecting a small number of important cases to yield the most information with greatest impact on the development of knowledge (Palinkas,2015).The sample was limited to published peer-reviewed journal articles and government documents because they have generally attained higher quality standards and they are a principle source of scholarly evidence (Hancock &Algozzine, 2015).A total of 19 documents were obtained and read with 11 articles selected for final analysis owing to their relevance and depth. The study employed qualitative analysis to identify the history, strengths and challenges faced by education policy reforms in Somalia (Kuckartz, 2014).

1.7 Background of the study

Historically, the education system in Somalia was dependent on Islamic methodology; Arabic language was medium of instruction in precolonial era. During the colonial period, British and Italians in traduced their languages into the Somali education system. Western donors consolidated the two systems in 1960 to assist education system in the country (Ministry of Education, 1976)

The history of colonial period, Somali's education system policy was disorganized and fragmented, that led to change its philosophy in post-independent to unify and address into the enrollment policy, curriculum activities, teacher training, text-books, medium of instruction. To achieve satisfactory levelin education system after the independence, the governments were determined to adopt suitable policies and strategies to improve the content of education in the country (Ministry of Education, 1976).

As part of unifying policy in education system after the independence, the system comprised of three levels—elementary, intermediate, and secondary, in which each of them was four years. Expansion of education was most vital option in Somalia during that period, so “at the advent of independence the total school population was 19,872. This increased to 42,156 in 1969.” According to Ministry of Education, year book, (1976):

Year/ Level	Elementary	Intermediate	Secondary	Total
1960-1961	16,332	22,790	750	19,872
1963-1964	20,848	4,818	1,117	25,666
1966-1967	21,050	7,532	2,218	30,800
1969-1970	23,842	14,129	4,185	42,156

(Source: Ministry of Education, 1976)

In the military period the policy encouraged a high level admission in the schools in general due to strong desire of local ownership of revolutionaries' policy. The Ministry of Education (1976) stated that “The total enrollment in the elementary schools increased from 23,842 in the school year 1969-1970 to 67,406 in 1973-1974. The intermediate schools also increased from 14,129 in the school year 1969-1970 to 25,688 in 1973-1974 and the secondary schools or their equivalent increased from 4,185 in the school year 1969-1970 to 10,586 in 1973-1974. (The Ministry of Education (1976).

From 1972, the policy encouraged those who passed the Centralized Intermediate Examination to eligible for admission in general and technical secondary schools or other post intermediate vocational schools. In spite of general schools there were facilities for post intermediate training in technical and commercial subjects, the length of training was varies from 2-4 years (Ministry of Education, 1976).

A Review of the Current Situation

Before 1973 there were three technical institutes in the country. One of them dealt with the construction trades such as carpentry and joinery and attached to it was a two-year clerical training center. Other deals with motor vehicle mechanics, farm equipment repair, general mechanics and electricity. In third technical institute – a four years secondary school in which general mechanics and electricity were included in a broad secondary programme. In that year a Maritime vocational school upgraded to a full Maritime and Fishery Institute, Agriculture Institute and a two years Polytechnic secondary school at Lafole started its admission. (Ministry of Education, 1976) On the other hand, the introduction of the Somali language as a medium of instruction in the schools was the most important step taken in the early seventies in education policies.

In terms of higher education policy, University Institute of Mogadishu was established in 1954, it grew out of Scuola Politica Administrative, an education center specifically designed for the speedy training of Somali officials in the art of public administration. Scuola Politica Amministrativa served as useful purpose in producing Somalis who were badly needed in the rapid Somalization of the administrative machinery. At a later stage, it was felt that a more formal university education was needed for highly administrative posts in civil service, so this feeling culminated in the establishment of the University Institute with faculty of Law and Economics. (Ministry of Education, 1976).

In academic year of 1970-71, the first group of students graduated from the faculty of law and economics. It was first time offered university degrees in Somalia. (Ministry of Education, 1976) Since that time great political desire has been given to broadening of the Somali National University (SNU).

From devastated conflict in 1991, Somalia has experienced in protracted turmoil; the violent conflict left whole Somalia without function government institutions including basic services such as education. Access to education remains, so far, limited, despite the fact that the private sector has restored schools and university studies in early time from 1995, teachers and instructors have been re-established, and curricula and textbooks transported from different countries assigned students but there was no governing body delegating national rules and policies on education system. Since the central government restored, it's unable to govern effectively in many socio-economic parts in the country, the ministry of education could not able framing establishment standards and quality assurance policies, providing substantial financial support in education, or imposing accountability for country education instrument. Thus education has been left largely up to community and individual efforts.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Conceptualization and Role of Education

International instruments and declarations proclaim the right of all individuals to have an education, which sets the foundation for the promotion of all human rights. The right to free expression, the right to equality and the right to have a voice in decision-making with regard to social and educational policies are integral parts of education. (United Nation University, Revitalizing Higher Education in Sub-Saharan Africa, project report, 2009)

A Review of the Current Situation

The world's commitment to the provision of education to all has a long history. The first such commitment was in 1948, when the Universal Declaration of Human Rights was published. In that declaration, education was recognized as a fundamental human right for the multifaceted development of individuals and of society. In particular, it was declared that elementary education should be free and compulsory and that the higher levels of education should be accessible to all on the basis of merit. (United Nations 1948). Why was education made such a critical focal point of the socio-economic and political development of nations in the first place? In the 1970s and 1980s, the view of education as a public good was given impetus by the evolution of human capital theory, which focused on in economics of education. Studies by the likes of Gary Schultz and George Psacharopoulos purported to have established a positive relationship between schooling and economic growth. They argued that both the individual and society benefited from an educated populace, that investing in education had both private and social rates of return. The argument was that "a more educated society may translate into higher rates of innovation, higher overall productivity through firms' ability to introduce new and better production methods, and a faster introduction of new technology"(EFA Global Monitoring Report, 2005, P 41).

The United Nations General Assembly adopted the Millennium Declaration in 2000. In formulating a plan for achieving the objectives of the declaration, it came up with 8 goals, 18 targets and 48 indicators that collectively came to be known as the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). The MDGs are "a set of time-bound and measurable goals and

targets designed to decrease poverty, hunger, disease, illiteracy, environmental devastation and discrimination against women” (Wagner, 2007). The MDGs obliged all governments to have in place programmes and strategies that will ensure achievement of the MDGs by 2015. But Somalia faced by internal big challenges to fulfill its MDG’ commitment and failed to improve one indicator of the goals specially the education sector.

2.2 Review of the Current Situation

Since rehabilitation started, the government’s ministry of education was dependent on a small grant from UN agencies randomly that meant the implementation of policy options and strategies in education system remains entirely dependent upon donors pooling funding.

The ministry of education with support of UN and other international organizations initiated efforts to reform the national education policy, but clear strategy framework collaboration was missed, so many duplicated documents have been made. There were three duplicated proposals since 2005, which one of them has never been approved by the parliament. (Ministry of Education, Planning Sector Report, 2015)

The last final draft of National Education Policy proposed in 2016 stated that “The absence of a consolidated Education Sector Policy document to address the education and training needs resulted in some departments and components operating as ‘islands’ and not ‘talking’ to each other as expected, thus leading to duplication of efforts and wastage of resources” (Ministry of Education, Culture and Higher Education, Policy Sector Report, 2016). This last draft of policy document endorsed by the cabinet, but the parliament has not yet approved it.

A Review of the Current Situation

In 2013, the Ministry of Human Development and Public Service (Six national sector services combined in one institution body) asked to share an idea with UNICEF to raise fund to the urgent need for expansion of education services. The program called the Go to School (G2S)^(*). (UNICEF, 2013-2016) the program was look like broad advertisement propoganda that was criticized by the local educator experts and private teachers (Al Jazeera Arabic 16/10/201). It rather seemed as an exaggerated advertisement slogan and self benefit program, because the reality of schooling revived in earlier 1995-1996 was not mentioned or indicated. The (Go2S) seemed as a start point now. However, The Minister and UNICEF proposed to targetone million children and youth in three years without a national plan and strategy in account, the effort was dependent on abeautiful dream and absolutely shining views in front of the donors. The challenge was big; one million students in one year without basic education architecture and national planning were incredible. To achieve like this ambitious goal there must be a strong commitment in the national level.

The first step, the program inevitably needed for a significant fund, aninterim support from international NGO's was not enough; so, the government committedto pay 50% of go to schoolteachers' salary, the amount was (100\$). But the promise not fulfilled by the government; so many teachers are left without any predictable form of remuneration. The program totally collapsed.

(*) Go to School or Back to School campaigns in over 55 countries since 1994 following the Rwandan genocide. These initiatives have become powerful strategies in facilitating access to learning for millions of children. These concerted efforts have helped to raise the credibility of both the government and a right-based approach to education. (UNICEF 2016)

The Somali national education financial strategy still is in critical point, over all education national budget remains very low, so the role of the government to coordinate education services inequities between the regions and districts, and also public and private levels. For instance, in the last two years the ministry of education of federal government started to implement centralized secondary school leaving certificate examination on private schools in Mogadishu and surround area, although the ministry has never had one class of secondary school since 1991, you may ask what sort of content applying on the student learning evaluation. If many people say it's a very good step forward into the real governing mechanism, but what good for what? In this case, the private education umbrellas own their secondary examination and certification in parallel. So, the two different examination results in one student; how the result will be valid to certify the student outcome, if the two outcomes are not matching each other? Really, this double standards in the reliability of two parallel learning outcomes causes psychological impact on the students and their parents, due to lack of education policy giving consideration for what they learned only.

The ministry's efforts facing now many challenges to take its roles, for instance:

- There is no clear education policy approved up till now, many-duplicated meeting efforts were made without necessary outcomes.
- All School building rehabilitation in Mogadishu and some areas in the other regions inaugurated, but the ministry has no capability to run it, due to resource capacity.

A Review of the Current Situation

- Teacher's issue is more critical point; in terms of their preparation policy, certification, licensing, recruiting, training and the salary rate. The teachers' salary is not same rate of other civil servants who is working in the government institutions, so the impact the inequities of qualifications would be disastrous in the education fieldwork and quality assuring policy.
- Lack of clear policy and strategy about public and private partnership in national education framework.
- There is also lack of reliable data related entire education framework in Somalia, the ministry Statistical Yearbooks data validation is questionable, because many gaps werenot considered. (National Education Statistical Yearbook, Federal republic of Somalia, 2013-2014).

In terms of higher education, the situation reflects that prevailing at other levels of the education system. Although the system developed considerably in the level of quantity, but some universities studying conditions are not keeping in track; due to increasing number of universities with poor infrastructure and adequate resource, lack of supply and learning materials, while laboratories and library facilities are insufficient.

2.3 Quality Issues in Education Policy

Since the World Conference on Education For All, which took place in Jomtien, Thailand (UNDP, UNESCO, UNICEF and IBRD, 1990), and the World Education Forum of Dakar (UNESCO, 2000), the recommendations submitted during major international meetings and the accompanying research have all placed emphasis on quality.

On the quality front, policies need to be developed that will ensure improvement of the quality of education provided. It is generally accepted in the literature that the concept of quality is a contested one, primarily because it is a relative (as opposed to absolute) concept. What might be considered, as quality education today may not be quality education tomorrow? For this reason, it is pointless to search for a fixed definition of “quality education”. Rather, it is conventional to describe quality in education in terms of such indicators as the percentage of trained teachers, pupil–textbook ratios and pupil–teacher ratios. (United Nation University, project report, 2009)

Quality is mainly the result of a combination of five factors. The first of these relates to policies on education, which in turn leads to the second factor, financing. The third factor has to do with enrolment and retention. The fourth concerns mainly content and teaching strategies, while the fifth is devoted to human and material resources. Among these five factors, two appear to have a significant impact on the outcomes of educational action: first, contents and strategies and, second, resources. Contents and strategies are important because they reflect political orientations and put them into operation in the form of educational measures that can be effectively observed. Resources, meanwhile, form a series of relevant indicators regarding the determination to implement policy decisions. Programmes, strategies and resources are vital for education because they play a direct role in shaping people and in helping them to achieve personal fulfillment as individuals, citizens and producers. This explains, through a retroactive loop effect the vital role-played by education in human development (Morin, 1986)

A Review of the Current Situation

Definitions of quality education are as an indication of the outcomes of a concerted progressive process. For example, Hawes and Stephens (1990) define it as “a process that requires efficiency in meeting the set goals, relevance to human and developmental needs and conditions, something more in relation to the pursuit of excellence and human betterment”.

Otherwise, Bandary (2005) states that “quality education encompasses a range of elements including the level of student achievement; the ability and qualification of staff; the standard of facilities and equipment; the effectiveness of teaching, planning and administrative processes; and the relevance of programmes to the needs of students and the nation in an emerging global knowledge economy”. However, others view quality as both a process and a critical indicator of expected outcomes. Schaeffer (1992) asserts “quality education involves how people are mobilized and empowered through the provision of knowledge and skills to enable them to participate in the democratic structures of their societies”.

In spite of the variations in definitions, there is a clear consensus that the provision of education is not only a quantitative process but is also qualitative. “The Dakar Framework for Action in 2000 recognized the quality of education as a primary determinant of whether or not Education for All is achieved. The second of the six goals of the Framework committed signatory nations to the provision of primary education of good quality, while the sixth goal implored nations to make a commitment to improve all aspects of education so that everyone can achieve better learning outcomes” UNESCO (2004).

2.4 Education Language Policy

Hence national language policy and the selection of languages to be taught in school and used as the media of instruction are considerable importance for the quality of teaching and learning. It is a policy choice with implications for curriculum goals, content and pedagogy. It is also an intensely political matter. The Somali language plays role of unity medium of instruction, if the new decentralized education policy definitely organized. In terms of Arabic language, it seems in strong position through Quran learning, but needs only political facilitation in the classroom.

“Educational policy makers have difficult decisions to make with regard to languages, schooling and the curriculum in which the technical and the political overlap. While there are strong educational arguments in favor of the mother tongue, a careful balance also needs to be made between enabling people to use local languages in learning and providing access to global languages of communication through education” UNESCO (2003). In general, it seems to be accepted that initial literacy programmes in the mother tongue facilitate the learning of a second language as the medium of instruction. “The introduction of national language as the main medium of education does not exclude the urgency of introducing a second language of international communication in education. A second language should be introduced into the educational system as early as possible. The experiences have shown that children learn and master languages more easily when they start at a very young age”. (The EFA Global Monitoring Report 2005, UNESCO 2004:154).

A Review of the Current Situation

However, the major languages of international communication used in numerous education systems in Somalia should be retained by improving their teaching and practice. Adding a second language of international communication in the education system will depend on the existence of a first language of a similar nature. A major argument in favor of introducing a second language as early as possible in early childhood, or at the beginning of primary education is based on improving communication between linguistic areas dominated by languages such as Arabic, English, etc. In terms of innovative programmes for the introduction of several languages in education, puts forward consistent arguments in favor of a gradual strategy. It would appear that: “There is now a strong body of evidence that bilingual schooling offers significant benefits in learning outcomes. In the most successful models, the mother tongue is used in the early years of schooling so that children can acquire and develop the literacy skills that enable fuller participation in learning activities. In a growing number of countries, after four or five years (earlier in some cases) there is a transition to learning and using the second or foreign language as the medium of instruction. In this way, initial literacy is acquired more easily, facilitating the acquisition of the language that will become the medium of instruction for the rest of the school years”(The EFA Global Monitoring Report 2005, and UNESCO 2004:154–156)

In Somalia, a growing number of primary schools offer the pupils Arabic/English lessons, in addition to Somali language, the official language of instruction. In line with a post conflict reform of curricula, particular emphasis has been placed on teaching in the mother tongue,

the first language of pupils during the first stage of basic education. But there is a question of initiating education in the mother tongue or first language of learners in order to establish basic skills, and then gradually move towards Arabic/English, so the second stage of basic education, the national language becoming a subject of teaching in this cycle. (Ministry of Education, Culture and Higher Education, Education act draft 2015)

The education governing in Somalia needs national education policy reforms to improve education qualities and standards. It can be reflected in these areas:

1. **Policy formulation.** Government education priorities focusing on free access to schooling for all, and enact flexible policies to promote inclusion and education quality.
2. **Planning and implementation,** monitoring and evaluating the education programmes for national and international educational policies and standards and the learning needs considered to be in action.
3. **Coordination.** Good coordination mechanism for education, including effective information sharing between federal and regional administrations maintained.
4. **Curricula.** Culturally, socially and linguistically relevant curricula are used to provide formal and non-formal education, appropriate to the regional and district levels.
5. **Instruction.** Instruction is learner-centred, participatory and justice.
6. **Measurement and Evaluation.** Appropriate methods, systematic and impartial evaluation in order to improve practice and validate learning achievements needed.

A Review of the Current Situation

7. **Training.** Teachers and other education personnel receive periodic, relevant and structured training according to need and circumstances.
8. **Recruitment and selection.** A sufficient number of appropriately qualified teachers and other education personnel are required through a participatory and transparent process based on selection criteria that reflect diversity and equity.
9. **Conditions of work.** Teachers and other education personnel have clearly defined conditions of work, follow a code of conduct and are appropriately compensated.
10. **Supervision and support.** Supervision and support mechanisms to be established for teachers and other education personnel, and are used on a regular basis.

In Somalia, there are challenges needs to identify and to set on the possible policy priorities and legal framework, such as follows:

<i>Challenges</i>	<i>Possible education policy priorities</i>
1- Limited access to educational opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Abolishment of school fees. • Relieving parents of indirect educational costs (related to such items as transport, uniforms, text book costs, etc.) • Continuous assessment of effective use of the available space in schools, with a view towards ensuring its optimum use.
2- Low funding of education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing budget allocation to education to at least 6% of the national budget, as per the recommendations of the world Education Forum held in Dakar, Senegal, in 2000. • Identification of diverse sources of funding for education.

<i>Challenges</i>	<i>Possible education policy priorities</i>
3-Illiteracy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognition of and support for the role of community organizations in the promotion of literacy. • Striving for and consolidating partnerships between public and private institutions in literacy delivery. • Combining literacy delivery strategies of campaigns, programmes and projects to enhance the advantages of each.
4- Quality and relevance of education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of a life skills curriculum as well as the capacity to deliver such a curriculum. • Promotion of high-quality and relevant vocational education programmes. • Reforming curricula to incorporate contextual issues in their content. • Encouraging community participation in education. • Training and deploying qualified teachers.

2.5 Decentralized of Education governing policy (USA pilot)

Somalia is facing contemporary challenge on how couldbe managed the decentralized education system in current newly established regional states. Until now there is no clear policy defined in this context, in many countries dependent on decentralized systemin their education administration Decentralized of education system infederal countries gives in three different levels of authorities to make and implement education policy, beginning with the federal, state and local governments. For instance,the USA has highly decentralized system of education; the federal government, although playing an important role in education, does not establish or license schools or govern educational institutions at any level except schools, which serve the children of

A Review of the Current Situation

military personnel stationed overseas, operated by the department of defense; and the five service academies of the Army, Air Force, Navy, Coast Guard and Merchant Marine, the general authority to create and administer public schools is reserved for the states. (US Department of Education, education in the United States: A Brief Overview, September 2005)

In USA, the Congress is the federal lawmaking body and has passed numerous laws directly and indirectly affecting education, but the Department of Education is the primary agency of the federal government that implements the laws that congress enacts to support education at the federal level. In doing so, the department establishes policy for, administers and coordinates much of federal financial assistance for education. Its stated mission is to ensure equal access to education and to promote educational excellence throughout the nation. US Department of Education (2005).

The Department's major activities are the following: US Department of Education, (2005)

- 1- Implementing laws related to federal financial assistance for education, administering distribution of those funds and monitoring their use. The Department distributes financial assistance to eligible applicants throughout the nation for elementary, secondary and college education; for education of individuals with disabilities and individuals who are illiterate, disadvantaged.
- 2- Collecting data and oversees research on America's schools and disseminating this information to educators and the general public. The Department oversees research on most aspects of education;

collecting data on trends; and gathers information to help identify approaches, ideas and successful teaching techniques. Employees of the department as well as contractors and grant recipients, conduct the research.

- 3- Identifying the major issues and problems in education and focusing national attention on them. The Secretary advises the president and leads the department in implementing the president's education policies- from the preparation of legislative proposals for congress to decisions about education priorities.
- 4- Enforcing federal laws prohibiting discrimination in programs and activities that receive federal funds.

In most states, the topic of education is addressed in the state constitution, with the state legislature having the ultimate authority over education matters. This authority includes enacting education-related legislation and appropriating state funds for education.

Generally, state legislature delegates a significant amount of policy-making authority to the state board of education. State boards of education are bodies of citizens appointed by the legislature or governor, or popularly elected. The board is responsible for approving statewide education policies and determining budget priorities. In some cases, the state board is responsible for all levels of education, including vocational and post-secondary education, while in many states the board concentrates on education at elementary and secondary levels. Most states have state department of education that serves as the executive agency for education. A chief state school officer is generally responsible for overseeing the state department of education and reporting periodically to

A Review of the Current Situation

the state board of education, the legislature and the governor. This person may be called superintendent, commissioner, director or secretary of education. The state board of education or the governor appoints most chief state school officers, while some are popularly elected. US Department of Education, (2005)

In most cases, State governments are responsible for the following:

- Developing curriculum guidelines and performing standards;
- Providing technical assistance to school districts;
- Licensing private elementary and secondary schools to operate within their jurisdictions;
- Licensing or certifying school teachers and administrators;
- Administering statewide student achievement tests;
- Developing accountability plans and reporting on student performance to the USA Department of Education.
- Defining minimum requirements for high school graduation;
- Distributing state and federal funding to school districts; and
- Establishing the minimum number of school days per year.

In terms of local governments, although state government has an ultimate authority over education, most states delegate some decision-making powers and the operation of public elementary and secondary schools to local education agencies, or school districts. Most states give districts considerable authority to determine school budgets and to implement curriculum. In fact, many school districts further delegate decision-making and budgetary authority to individual schools, a practice known as site-based (or school-based) management. Each district has a local school board, governing district schools, their policies generally

conform to the regulations of the state board and statutes of the state legislature, district school board members generally elected or nominated popularly. The school board selects and hires the district superintendent, who is responsible for implementing policy and managing the day-to-day operations of the school district. Their responsibility as the following: US Department of Education, (2005)

- Determining the budget;
- Allocating money to individual schools and programs;
- Hiring teachers and other staff;
- Preparing and disseminating annual reports on student performance;
- Setting teachers and administrator salaries;
- Implementing the curriculum;
- Planning and administering teacher in-service training;
- Constructing and maintaining school buildings; and
- Purchasing equipment and supplies.

In this context, Somalia facing decentralized system in service delivering in state and local level, the lessons learned in suitable decentralized power sharing and encouraging ownership of the grassroots people could be efficient way to deliver education in Somalia.

Discussion of Findings

The study used a documentary study review method to collect and analyze data available in the field notes and documents to determine key concepts. The main data resources used include:

- Ministry interim education sector policy and strategy plan (2013-2014).
- Ministry Education Management Information System (EMIS) database of 2011-2016.

A Review of the Current Situation

- Statistics book, developed by the ministry of Education with support of UNICEF, 2016
- Ministry of education EMIS database, School Survey Report (2012-2013).
- Teacher Profile Reports from, UNICEF, 2013-2016.
- Somalia, data set on schools from 2011-2016, OCHA.
- Somalia, Millennium Development Goals progress Report, UNDP, 2010.

The core analysis discussed on the education policy system used by the ministry of education, especially on the current private schools and universities. There were different challenges mainly concerning the overlapping and duplicating efforts to reform education system policy that delegated by UN agencies and some international NGOs since 2010. However, the ministry of education still has no national education policy and legal procedures framework approved from the parliament to control the decentralized education quality and standards system. The consequences still remains in high level of malpractice in learning outcomes and certification. The private sector is the only mainstream providing education services, regardless the quality, inclusive and equity with or without NGOs pattern.

The challenge also related to the political transformation system in the country. The different regional administrations has no clear decentralized service delivery system and coherent political structures with the central government, which maintains their participation in the national level governing process, so the problem is to adopt new national education policy reforms without stable constitutional framework. In this regard education relies on the people at many levels of the government; it

needs to design to lead to a quality education for every Somali child. Achieving this goal, it depends on good practices in single national policy that can address highly qualified teachers providing students high quality standard of education. It depends on top-down decentralized regular assessment to see what's working and what isn't. It depends on also to involve parents with good choices and information.

The main findings of the study include:

1. In the post conflict, primary enrolment was started but not enough and the role of private services providers varies greatly across regions in the country, while public education service is absent in many parts of the country.
2. The current policy guideline process is the key challenges. The capacity of the ministry to address the challenges is likely remaining unclear, due to lack of domestic policies and insufficient deficient budget, while the donor's seems a grant schemes priority for the ministry.
3. The government has no functioning schools in many parts of the country, the service provided by private schools and universities although crucial are not sufficient.
4. In the absence of central accreditation and quality control bodies resulted diverse patterns of ownership, management, and finance. So, the communities own the Majority of the schools and universities are private whereas some owned by individuals represent a substantial percentage of school owners. In this circumstance, such proliferation caused poor quality and poor resources affected the education system.

Conclusion & Recommendations

The study is dependent on documentary review method, the data demonstrated many challenges and opportunities about recovery of national education policy after profound destruction of education facilities and after education guided by a draft education policy which has never become into a full policy that addresses all issues related to decentralized education system, showing the needs of the local quality improvement. Based on the findings, the study presents the following recommendations:

1. Ministry of education capacity must be addressed especially its national education budget to lead educational access and quality policies in clude more closely decentralized education system.
2. To set up a road map in national education policy reforms guideline in decentralized system, especially in good access for all and high quality and standards drawn from unique revise policy in the whole education levels of Somali federal government.
3. To develop a national education policy and legal procedures frame work with high level participation of the regional administration, approved from the parliament to control the decentralized education quality and standards system.
4. To give more emphasis on public and private partnership in education service delivery.
5. To organize high level of advocacy by the Somali Federal Republic to comprehensive awareness of the importance to increase the national budget for educational support and development.

6. Ministry of education should open more local government schools in the different federal states to expand public education services.
7. This study used documentary review method to collect data. However, it is possible that the review may not contain all the related policies and education reforms, for more benefit the study recommends applying other methodologies of data collection such as quantitative surveys in the future studies.

References

- Al Jazeera Arabic, The Campaign for Education in Somalia, <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DI8KzrNB1c016/10/2013>
- Bandary, M. S. (2005). "Meeting the Challenges: The Development of Quality Assurance in Oman's Colleges of Education", *Higher Education*, Vol. 50, pp. 181–195.
- Brickman, W. W., & Fraser, S. E. (1968). *A history of international and comparative education: Nineteenth-century documents*. Glenview, IL: Scott, Foresman and Company.
- Carnoy, M. (2005). *Globalization, educational trends and the open society*. Paper presented at the Open Society Institute Education Conference, Stanford.
- Education in the United States: A Brief Overview, US Department of Education, September 2005.
- Gaborone, B. (2006). The use of documentary research methods in social research. *African Sociological Review*, 10, 221–230.
- Hancock, D. R., & Algozzine, B. (2015). *Doing case study research: A practical guide for beginning researchers*. New York, NY: Teachers College Press.
- Hawes, H. and Stephens, D. (1990) *Questions of Quality: Primary Education and Development*. Essex, England: Longman. (p. 11)
- Kuckartz, U. (2014). *Qualitative text analysis: A guide to methods, practice and using software*. London: Sage. P 23
- Ministry of Education, Year Book 1976
- Ministry of Education, Planning Sector Report, 2015
- Ministry of Education, Culture and Higher Education, Policy Sector Report. 2016
- Morin, E. (1986). *The Method of quality*, Paris: Editions du Seuil. p 54
- Nogueira, F., Jaana, F. (2013). *A comparative analysis: The politics of access to higher education*.

- Palinkas, L. A., Horwitz, S. M., Green, C. A., Wisdom, J. P., Duan, N., & Hoagwood, K. (2015). Purposeful sampling for qualitative data collection and analysis in mixed method implementation research. *Administration and Policy in Mental Health and Mental Health Services Research*, 42, 533–544.10.1007/s10488-013-0528-y
- Schaeffer, S. (1992). “Education Quality Redefined”. In. Rawley, C. and Summa, P. (eds.), *Redefined Quality. The Forum For Advanced Basic Education and Literacy*, Vol. 1 (3), pp. 1–2.
- Segrera, F. L. (2010). *Trends and innovations education reform: Worldwide, Latin America and in the Caribbean*. Center for Studies in Higher Education. Research & Occasional Paper Series: CSHE.12.10.
- UNESCO, (2003). *Global Monitoring Report, 2003*. Paris: UNESCO.
- UNESCO (2004). *Education For All Global Monitoring Report 2005: Education for All, the Quality Imperative*. Paris: UNESCO.
- UNESCO (2005). *Education Today: The Newsletter of UNESCO’s Education Sector*. No. 15, October 2005 to January 2006.
- UNESCO (2006). *Global Monitoring Report, 2006*. Paris: UNESCO. UNESCO-BREDA (2005). *EFA in Africa: Paving the Way for Action*.
- UNESCO. United Nations (1948). *Universal Declarations of Human Rights*. New York.
- United Nations (2007). *Millennium Development Goals Report 2007*. New York.
- United Nations (1948). *Universal Declarations of Human Rights*. New York.
- United Nation University, Revitalizing Higher Education in Sub-Saharan Africa, project report, 2009, p 9)
- Wagner, D. (2007). “2000 Millennium Development Goals” (available at <http://www.uiowa.edu/ifdebook/fag/MDG.shtml>)
- attention to those barriers existing within some of the developing countries.